

Link Load Balance Using Randomised Method On 2D NoC

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Abstract: Network on Chip (NoC) seems like a good way to build high-performance networks communication in the present and future. IP cores (Intellectual Propriety) and switches are the building blocks of a NoC that are connected by communication channel but the communication channel becomes congested due to central part of the network because heavy loads come from neighbour nodes. The system's performance will undoubtedly suffer from congestion brought on by nearby nodes, which will also negatively impact the other nodes. So, routing algorithm performance has a major issue on NoC communication. The communication architecture of NoC mainly based on topology model, routing algorithm or architecture model and switching techniques model. One of the fundamental components of 2D NOC matrix is the routing algorithm. Data from the source router to destination router is one of the key concern of routing architecture model. So, we are utilizing different nearby route to reduce local delay that is caused by congestion by the methods of random route calculation strategy to minimize delay and congestion.

Key-Words: Network on Chip (NoC), Intellectual Propriety (IP), Routing

I. INTRODUCTION

Introduction: Implementation of SoC (System-on-Chip) that is built up by many processors and communication channels need to make synchronize among processors through communication channels that becomes very critical when a wide range of functions with different latency and bandwidth needs need to be supported by a connection fabric. The silicon industry has chosen Network-on-Chip (NoC) as one interconnect fabric approach to link dozens of processor units and heterogeneous resources [1]. With the high demands of various processors and communication channels the communications channel becomes high loaded and face traffic jam. This paper presents an alternative approach to reduce load balancing for Network-on-Chip (SoC) [2] systems that reduces heavy traffic and variable bitrate communication channels. It is predicated that load balancing using random routing over NoC that monitors the route weight (route load) based on router energy and traffic queue of the router buffer. Overloaded communication links or channels [3] and nodes or hopes may consume high energy in when forwarding data from one node to another node using those communication channels as a result it may become unstable state in network and may performance deteriorate. Load-balancing [4] is method that distribute the network traffic by using three important parameters one is nodes energy, average data packet on queue and number of nodes along with the weight of nodes [5] and link values. Using load balancing it assist to reduce congestion; power consumption also reduced end to end delivery time. Using proper load balancing it achieves the entire network works lifetime.

II. RELATED WORK

In this part we provide a quick overview of other authors idea that are used to the evaluate of the network load status when it communicates at the running state. We make summary that will assist in distinguishing our tactics and design approach, which will be presented in next Section. The first work of this section the authors [3] put up a link utilization-based load balancing plan for NoCs. Congestion-Controlled Best-Effort (CCBE) [7], the communication service level on which the method is based, enables load control based on crucial shared resource utilization metrics. As a metric of congestion, they employ link utilization [10]. Hardware probes carry out these measures, which are then transmitted via dedicated service links in the matrix of NoC to ensure that there is no congestion in the communication. A similar approach can be used to create 3the path [11] that communicates the calculated loads of nodes to the processing unit of nodes.

The proper loads for the CCBE connections are decided by the controller of nodes, a Model Predictive Controller (MPC) [12]. The authors' approach necessitates that routing in the NoC not be dynamic.

Based on source rate utility maximization [14], the authors presented a flow of link's control technique for the best effort (BE) [13] load traffic balance in NoC. They modelled flow control of link to get maximization of link load problem with connection capacity constraints. These authors assumed that the use of link allocation is the best-effort sources [15] is the primary function of the upgrading issue and that the assured services of links in the NoC is being maintained at the intended level. In order to control of link load is the best-effort is the source rates, the optimization problem had to be solved. It resulted in a continual technique that can be utilized to find the best BE node's source rates that is to manage by the NoC's congestion [16]. The suggested algorithm is used by a centralized processor or controller.

However, there are so many link-load balance designs to try to reduce traffic during mapping and routing on NoC. In this research, we present a shortest random routing design methodology to ensure link-load balance while minimizing NoC link load, energy consumption high speed communication.

III. PROPOSED WORK / ROUTE OR LINK DESIGN OF NOC

The 2D matrix NoC communication between different nodes is happened by different communication channels or links. The nodes and communication channel always remain busy to make communication with each other's. The communication between source to destination remains one or more nodes and communication links. The diagram of 2D NoC [7] is depicted

Fig1. NoC Diagram

as the main aim of this project is to plan and execute a load balance routing algorithm, characterized by a unique combination of routing techniques on a 2D NoC using randomized mathematical formula for better load balancing, higher path diversity, scalability and speed per port and simpler switch design. Traditionally we saw a dedicated shortest line between source to destination [9] but the same line and node help

to communicate other sources and destinations also. If the same lines and nodes helps the others sources and destinations to establish the communication it becomes to high loaded that makes to low latency, high power consumptions, low throughput and some time it become hung the communication channel. To avoid those problems, we can take an alternative theory that we summarised here. Suppose we want make link from S to D that is $S \rightarrow D$ we must prefer and find the shortest path, we follow the shortest path but if the others source and destination make the link using this path it increases the link loads may face the above mention problems. To avoid those problems, we find, use and calculate the nearest shortest path using randomised formula that helps to find alternative shortest path to avoid the above said problems.

Algorithm of the proposed work

01. Start
02. Find shortest path and make the connection from source to destination.
03. If source to destination link and nodes are low loaded
04. Then route is low loaded and make the connection for data sharing.
05. If source destination link and nodes are moderate or medium loaded
- 05.1. Then
- 05.2. If there is/are another low loaded route exists
- 05.3. Use this low loaded route
- 05.4. Else
- 05.5. Use same route
06. If source to destination link and nodes are high Loaded
07. If there is/are another low loaded route exists
08. Use this low loaded route
09. Else
10. Use same route
11. If link and nodes high loaded condition exit
12. Then
13. Do not use that route.
14. If there exists another path
15. Use this path
16. Else
17. Fault may occur
18. End

IV. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

We want to present a low-Energy consumption, low latency from source to destination communication on 2D NoC architecture [10] using alternative randomised shortest path link through nodes. On this architecture we use a randomise shortest near path selection scheme

that find and use low-energy consumption, low latency path. Problems low execution of the previous architecture, links congestion to transfer information from each router's to neighbouring routers is updated one by one that shows it is in almost real-time updates all nodes. But we prove that the links and nodes energy consumption by our randomise shortest near path routing is also reduced the network delay and low energy consumption. Results of using our mathematical methods show a better output using the of nearest-shortest link using neighbour node traffic. In the future by our model we want to explore better architectural output by reducing the delay to a multiple step to gain better congestion information in link and nodes, and launch more characters in our experiment. To show the performance we use some randomised formula and architecture that is given below then we also do this formula using the C language and get better performance using all others link and communication nodes. Here we use this formula with values and give the output that is simulated simply on TurboC.

Fig 2: NoC Transition

Load value calculation of the shortest path and the nearest shortest path.

$$PW_{(pi)} = X_1 * NE_{(pi)} - X_2 * ANTQ_{(pi)} - X_3 * HC_{(pi)}$$

Where

$PW_{(pi)}$ – Load value of path Pi.

X_1, X_2, X_3 are constant – Where $X_1 + X_2 + X_3 = 1$ and $X_1 = .6, X_2$ and X_3 are equal $X_2 = .2, X_3 = .2$.

$NE_{(pi)}$ – Router Energy = Max { $RE_{n1}, RE_{n2}, RE_{n3}, RENm$ }.

$ANTQ_{(pi)}$ – Average Node Traffic Queue = (($ANTQ_{(n1)} + ANTQ_{(n2)} + \dots + ANTQ_{(nm)}$) /

m-1**Energy calculation of the shortest path and the nearest shortest path.**

$$E[NP_{(vi,vj)}] = (|NP_{(vi,vj)}| + 1) * ER + |NP_{(vi,vj)}| * EL.$$

Where

$|NP_{(vi,vj)}|$ - Hop of the path.

ER – Energy consumptions of single router.

EL - Energy consumptions of single link.

End to End Link Node Delay calculation of the shortest path and the nearest shortest path.

$$EDM = \sum_j \text{to } h \text{ TE.}$$

Where

TE =

$$\sum (\eta_{k,a} * (DC_{k,a} + ELT_{(k,a)})) + ELT_{k,a}.$$

$\eta_{k,a}$ – Packets wait to transfer on from link node i to node n to by link a.

$DC_{k,a}$ - Contention Delay. (Here Half of TQ).

$ELT_{(k,a)}$ – Link transmission time of data by spend time by sending a packet over link node a to node k.

Performance Evaluation

Using the above formula, we calculate the link and node load, energy consumption and delay.

Load Calculation Equation

$$W_{(p1)} = X_1 * NRE_{(p1)} - X_2 * ANTQ_{(p1)} - X_3 *$$

$$HC_{(p1)}. W_{(p1)} = X_1 * RE_{(p1)} - X_2 * ATQ_{(p1)} -$$

$$X_3 * HC_{(p1)}.$$

$$= .6 * 4.70 - .2 * .37 - .2 * 4$$

$$= 2.82 - .746 - .8$$

$$= 1.274 \text{ mj.}$$

$$W_{(p2)} = X_1 * RE_{(p2)} - X_2 * ATQ_{(p2)} - X_3 * HC_{(p2)}.$$

$$= .6 * 3.82 - .2 * .23 - .2 * 6$$

$$= 2.292 - .46 - 1.2$$

$$= 2.292 - 1.65$$

$$= .632 \text{ mj.}$$

$$W_{(p3)} = X_1 * RE_{(p3)} - X_2 * ATQ_{(p3)} - X_3 * HC_{(p3)}.$$

$$= .6 * 4.50 - .2 * 3.68 - .2 * 6$$

$$= 2.70 - .736 - 1.2$$

$$= .764 \text{ mj.}$$

End to End Calculation Equation

$$EDM = \sum_j \text{to } h \text{ TE.}$$

Where

$$TE = \sum (\eta_{k,a} * (DC_{k,a} + ELT_{(k,a)})) + ELT_{k,a}$$

FOR PATH 1

$$\begin{aligned} TE &= \sum (\eta_{k,a} * (DC_{k,a} + ELT_{(k,a)})) + ELT_{k,a} \\ &= ((.40+.38+.34) * [(.20+.18+.16) + (.210 + .202 + .200 + .210)]) + (.210 + .202 + .200 + .210) \\ &= 1.12 * [.54 + .822] + .822 \\ &= 1.12 * 1.362 + 822 \\ &= 2.23474 \text{ ns.} \end{aligned}$$

FOR PATH 2

$$\begin{aligned} TE &= \sum (\eta_{k,a} * (DC_{k,a} + ELT_{(k,a)})) + ELT_{k,a} \\ &= ((.30+.33+.20+.17+.15) * [(.15+.16+.10+.9+.7) + (.157+.173+.105+114+.89+.78)]) + (.157+.173+.105+114+.89+.78) \\ &= 1.15 * (.565+.722) + .722 \\ &= 1.15 * 1.287 + .722 \\ &= 1.48005 + .722 \\ &= 2.20205 \text{ ns.} \end{aligned}$$

FOR PATH 3

$$TE = \sum (\eta_{k,a} * (DC_{k,a} + ELT_{(k,a)})) + ELT_{k,a}$$

Energy calculation Equation

$$E[NP_{(vi,vj)}] = ((|NP_{(vi,vj)}| + 1) * ER) + (|NP_{(vi,vj)}| * EL).$$

FOR PATH 1

$$\begin{aligned} E[NP_{(vi,vj)}] &= ((|NP_{(vi,vj)}| + 1) * ER) + (|NP_{(vi,vj)}| * EL). \\ &= [(1+1) * 4.70 + (1+1) * 4.46 + (1+1) * 4.10 + (1+1) * 4.70] + ((1 * .210) + (1 * .202) + (1 * .200) + (1 * .210)) \\ &= [2 * 4.70 + 2 * 4.46 + 2 * 4.10 + 2 * 4.70] + (.210 + .202 + .200 + .210) \\ &= (.94 + .892 + .82 + .94) + .822 \\ &= 3.592 + .822 \\ &= 4.414 \text{ mj.} \end{aligned}$$

FOR PATH 2

$$\begin{aligned} E[NP_{(vi,vj)}] &= ((|NP_{(vi,vj)}| + 1) * ER) + (|NP_{(vi,vj)}| * EL). \\ &= [(1+1) * .352 + (1+1) * .387 + (1 * 1) * .234 + (1+1) * .199 + (1+1) * .176 + (1+1) * .269] + ((1 * .157) + (1 * .173) + (1 * .105) + (1 * .089) + (1 * .078) + (1 * .120)) \\ &= [.704 + .774 + .468 + .398 + .352 + .538] + (.157 + .173 + .105 + .089 + .078 + .120) \\ &= 3.234 + .722 \\ &= 3.956 \text{ mj.} \end{aligned}$$

Now give simulation result that is run on TurboC, First we compare our proposed 2D NoC architecture to evaluate the delay or latency and link or node power consume. Figure 3-6 shows also the result of randomised routing to indicate best to low performance when contrast to other load balancing method under non-uniform random traffic. Spatial randomised nearer shortest path traffic for load balancing in our randomised load balancing method, improve connectivity and reduce power consumption, low latency and smooth connectivity. Here we give three output of this

randomised nearer shortest path that is built up by nearly 1500 lines of code of C programming.

```

Turbo C++ IDE
Enter number of row and column of the 2D mesh NOC---->4
4

[ 390/30 ]--101--[ 280/29 ]--129--[ 293/23 ]--074--[ 218/29 ]
      |           |           |           |
      209         196         178         094
      |           |           |           |
[ 351/28 ]--202--[ 314/12 ]--207--[ 339/12 ]--174--[ 312/20 ]
      |           |           |           |
      069         087         141         165
      |           |           |           |
[ 342/27 ]--133--[ 281/10 ]--214--[ 184/37 ]--114--[ 430/14 ]
      |           |           |           |
      122         153         173         189
      |           |           |           |
[ 140/29 ]--131--[ 426/17 ]--186--[ 260/28 ]--156--[ 390/32 ]

In third braket value represent
Router Energy and Buffer present Status
Line represent Link Cost---->

<---NETWORK NO IS GIVEN BELOW--->

01 02 03 04
05 06 07 08
09 10 11 12
13 14 15 16

Enter Source Coordinate ----->13
Enter Destination Coordinate----->07

Source is correct and Source Coordinate is -----> 3 0
Destination is correct and Destination Coordinate is -----> 1 2
    
```

Fig 3: n x m 2D NoC router energy, buffer position and link cost.

```

Turbo C++ IDE
Destination is correct and Destination Coordinate is -----> 1 2

<---Total Path of the Network--->
Sno Degree Path
0 4 30 20 10 11 12
1 4 30 31 21 11 12
2 4 30 20 21 11 12
3 4 30 20 21 22 12
4 4 30 31 32 22 12
5 4 30 31 21 22 12

Select current path from serial no----->1
Current Status Of Path

Weight totalEC EndtoEndDelay Path
281.600 3578.000000 698.000000 30 31 21 11 12

After 1 Clock Cycle new value is--->
389 279 291 223
356 315 339 318
343 285 186 431
138 418 256 387

After 2 Clock Cycle new value is--->
384 281 291 224
351 321 333 323
345 289 185 426
140 414 253 382

After 3 Clock Cycle new value is--->
386 283 287 217
350 320 336 319
353 290 188 418
134 411 248 378

After 4 Clock Cycle new value is--->
392 278 293 225
345 317 335 317
352 293 181 416
126 404 256 382
    
```

Fig 4: n x m 2D NoC with source-destination and current EC, ETED and 4 clock cycle.

```

Turbo C++ IDE
392 278 293 225
345 317 335 317
352 293 181 416
126 404 256 382

<---After 4 Clock Cycle Network Status is--->
[ 392/30 ]--101--[ 278/29 ]--129--[ 293/23 ]--074--[ 225/29 ]
  |         |         |         |
  209       196       178       094
  |         |         |         |
[ 345/28 ]--202--[ 317/12 ]--207--[ 335/12 ]--174--[ 317/20 ]
  |         |         |         |
  069       087       141       165
  |         |         |         |
[ 352/27 ]--133--[ 293/10 ]--214--[ 181/37 ]--114--[ 416/14 ]
  |         |         |         |
  122       153       173       189
  |         |         |         |
[ 126/29 ]--131--[ 404/17 ]--186--[ 256/28 ]--156--[ 382/32 ]

Sno Degree  Acceptance  Weight  TotalEC          Delay  Path
0          4           Yes    271.000 3550.000      762.000 30 20 10 11 12
1          4           Yes    276.600 3528.000      698.000 30 31 21 11 12
2          4           Yes    244.800 3021.000      518.500 30 20 21 11 12
3          4           Yes    147.600 1973.000      443.500 30 20 21 22 12
4          4           Yes    214.000 2852.000      641.000 30 31 32 22 12
5          4           Yes    147.600 1973.000      443.500 30 31 21 22 12

<---Available Path is--->

Sno Degree  Path
0          4    30 20 10 11 12
1          4    30 31 21 11 12
2          4    30 20 21 11 12
3          4    30 20 21 22 12
4          4    30 31 32 22 12
5          4    30 31 21 22 12

Select current path from serial no----->1
    
```

Fig 5: n x m 2D NoC after 4 clock cycle NoC other available path with EC, ETED.

```

Turbo C++ IDE
[ 126/29 ]--131--[ 404/17 ]--186--[ 256/28 ]--156--[ 382/32 ]

Sno Degree  Acceptance  Weight  TotalEC          Delay  Path
0          4           Yes    271.000 3550.000      762.000 30 20 10 11 12
1          4           Yes    276.600 3528.000      698.000 30 31 21 11 12
2          4           Yes    244.800 3021.000      518.500 30 20 21 11 12
3          4           Yes    147.600 1973.000      443.500 30 20 21 22 12
4          4           Yes    214.000 2852.000      641.000 30 31 32 22 12
5          4           Yes    147.600 1973.000      443.500 30 31 21 22 12

<---Available Path is--->

Sno Degree  Path
0          4    30 20 10 11 12
1          4    30 31 21 11 12
2          4    30 20 21 11 12
3          4    30 20 21 22 12
4          4    30 31 32 22 12
5          4    30 31 21 22 12

Select current path from serial no----->1

Current Status Of Path

Weight  totalEC  EndtoEndDelay  Path
276.600 3528.000000 698.000000 30 31 21 11 12

<---After N Number of Clock Cycle Present Network Status is--->

Sno Degree  Acceptance  Weight  TotalEC          Delay  Path
0          4           Yes    147.600 1973.000      443.500 30 20 21 22 12
1          4           Yes    147.600 1973.000      443.500 30 31 21 22 12
2          4           Yes    214.000 2852.000      641.000 30 31 32 22 12
3          4           Yes    244.800 3021.000      518.500 30 20 21 11 12
4          4           Yes    271.000 3550.000      762.000 30 20 10 11 12
    
```

Fig 6: n x m 2D NoC other path EC, ETED.

V. CONCLUSION

Now conclude the paper by proposed the main concept on 2D NoC that is design for reduce low latency, low power consumption and reduce load on communication on link that is passing through various nodes. This algorithm proposed a new mathematical concept to reduce the above said problem using find the

best shortest nearest paths to alleviate the poor performance that it faces by the algorithm. In this study, Randomised NoC is a good option for Network-on-Chip SoCs that require load balancing in situations where the network experiences high traffic volumes of variable bitrate link flows. In terms of average delay, a normal best efforts method may be superior for low traffic with variable bitrate. The trials have also confirmed that our mathematical theory, which was stated in experimental Section, shows that NoCs with significant traffic of different section of link should be benefited for better load balancing.

REFERENCE

- [1]. Zhou Wenbiao, Yan Zhang, Zhigang Mao - Link-load Balance Aware Mapping and Routing for NoC - link-load Balance Aware Mapping and Routing for NoC 2007
- [2]. Marcelo Daniel Berejuck - Network-on-Chip with load balancing based on interleave of flits technique - ieeexplore
- [3]. Vanden Brand, J.W. and Ciordas, C. and Goossens, K. and Basten, T., 'Congestion Controlled Best-Effort Communication for Networks-on-Chip', Design, Automation Test in Europe Conference Exhibition, 2007, pp. 1 - 6. [4]. Talebi, M.S. and Jafari, F. and Khonsari, A, 'A Novel Flow Control Scheme for Best Effort Traffic in NoC Based on Source Rate Utility Maximization', 15th International Symposium on Modeling, Analysis, and Simulation of Computer and Telecommunication Systems (MASCOTS), 2007, Oct, pp. 381 - 386
- [5]. Jili Yan, Enhanced global congestion awareness (EGCA) for load balance in networksonchip, in Springer Science+Business Media, New York, 2015
- [6]. Mukund Ramakrishna, Vamsi Krishna Kodati and Paul V. Gratz, Member, IEEE, and Alexander Sprintson, GCA: Global Congestion Awareness for Load Balance in Networkson-Chip, IEEE Transactions on Parallel and Distributed Systems, 27(7), July 2016.
- [7]. Paul Gratz, Boris Grot and Stephen W. Keckler, Regional Congestion Awareness for Load Balance in Networks-on-Chip in 2008 IEEE.
- [8]. Luca Benini, University of Bologna, Giovanni De Micheli Stanford University, Networks on Chips: A New SoC Paradigm in 2002 IEEE.
- [9]. Masood Dehyadgari, Mohsen Nickray, Ali Afzalikusha and Zainalabein Navabi, Evaluation of Pseudo Adaptive XY Routing Using an Object-Oriented Model for NOC in 2005 IEEE.
- [10] U. Y. Ogras, P. Bogdan, and R. Marculescu, "An analytical approach for network-onchip performance analysis," IEEE Trans. Computer-Aided Design Integr. Circuits Syst., vol. 29, no. 12, pp. 2001–2013, Dec. 2010. [11] Davide Bertozzi, Antoine Jalabert and Srinivasan Murali, NoC Synthesis Flow for Customized Domain Specific Multiprocessor Systems-on-chip, IEEE Transactions on Parallel and Distributed Systems, 16(2), 2005, pp. 113–129.
- [12] Martin K.-F. and Thomas Hollstein and Heiko Zimmer and Manfred Glesner, DeadlockFree Routing and Component Placement for Irregular Mesh-based Networks-on-Chip, Proc of ICCAD'05, San Jose, CA, USA, pp.238-245, 2005.
- [13] J. Kennedy, R.C. Eberhart, Particle swarm optimization, Proc of ICNN'95, 12, 1995, pp. 1942– 1948.
- [14] Y. Shi, R. Eberhart, Empirical Study of Particle Swarm Optimization, Proc of CEC'99, Washington, DC, USA, 1999, pp.1945– 1950.
- [15] R. P. Dick, D. L. Rhodes, W. Wolf, TGFF: Task graphs for free, Proc of Int. Workshop Hardware/Software Codesign, Seattle, Washington, pp.97–101, 1998.
- [16] Y. Hoskote, S. Vangal, A. Singh, N. Borkar, and S. Borkar, "A 5-GHz mesh interconnect for a teraflops processor," IEEE Micro, vol. 27, no. 5, pp. 51–61, Sep.–Oct. 2007.
- [17] L. Chen and T. M. Pinkston, "NoRD: node-router decoupling for effective power-gating of on-chip routers," in Proceedings of MICRO, 2012.
- [18] T. Moscibroda and O. Mutlu, "A case for bufferless routing in on-chip networks," in Proceedings of the 36th International Symposium on Computer Architecture (ISCA), pp. 196–207, Jun. 2009.